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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Observations from space are a key aspect of astronomy for the well-known reasons of freedom from atmospheric weather, absorption and distortion. Access to, and participation in space observatories are an essential element of the LRP, for the entire range of astronomical research interests. Canada has played a significant role in past and ongoing space observatories, even as a very minor (~5%) partner, and has earned a deserved reputation for hardware, data handling, and scientific exploitation. The funding and support for these has largely come through the CSA, but the CSA budget for space science has eroded over the past decade or more, to the point of major concern. During the period of LRP2010, CSA has funded one very minor new facility - Hitomi - which had a disastrously short lifetime. The remaining LRP2010 priorities remain uncommitted, in spite of widespread interest and detailed studies. The decade ahead has major challenges if Canada is to have a viable and leadership role in space astronomy. This paper enumerates the issues and suggests what needs to be done to achieve a worthy space science program.

Lead author and affiliation John Hutchings, HAA

Email address of lead author john.hutchings@nrc.ca

Space Astronomy

LRP-2020 white paper

J.B. Hutchings, HAA, NRC
Locke Spencer, Univ of Lethbridge

Abstract/summary

Observations from space are a key aspect of astronomy for the well-known reasons of freedom from atmospheric weather, absorption and distortion. Access to, and participation in space observatories are an essential element of the LRP, for the entire range of astronomical research interests.

Canada has played a significant role in past and ongoing space observatories, even as a very minor (~5%) partner, and has earned a deserved reputation for hardware, data handling, and scientific exploitation. The funding and support for these has largely come through the CSA, but the CSA budget for space science has eroded over the past decade or more, to the point of major concern. During the period of LRP2010, CSA has funded one very minor new facility - Hitomi - which had a disastrously short lifetime. Although the decade saw a successful Canadian contribution to Herschel and delivery of the instruments for JWST, the remaining LRP2010 priorities remain uncommitted, in spite of widespread interest and detailed studies. The decade ahead has major challenges if Canada is to have a viable and leadership role in space astronomy. This paper enumerates the issues and suggests what needs to be done to achieve a worthy space science program.

How we got here

Canadian astronomy research has relied on observations from space over the past 5 decades, and space astronomy continues to be a major aspect of our future planning. It is worth recounting this history in looking to future initiatives and opportunities. Space observations have always been risky, expensive, and subject to irreparable failure. They have evolved with (and often driven) technical advances and experience, but ultimately are the only way to access the full electromagnetic spectrum, free of terrestrial distortions, weather, and diurnal cycles. We have to be involved in space facilities as a significant part of any LRP.

Perhaps the first significant early space observation was Don Morton's UV spectra of O stars in Orion, taken in a rocket flight lasting only a few minutes in 1965. These spectra revealed huge P Cygni line profiles, not seen before, that are the signature of radiation-driven mass loss that affects the evolution of all hot stars.

The following decade saw Canadians involved in the evolution of UV space facilities, including the NASA OAO series, the IUE, and in the early HST instruments. The parallel development of X-ray space astronomy included significant investigations by Canadians. Canadians were members of TAC and advisory committees, in recognition of our scientific interests and experience. Long before CSA was formed, Canada was a key partner, with NASA and Australia, in the proposed Starlab 1m UV telescope, which ultimately never flew, but gave Canada a first taste of the hardware and technology involved in space astronomy. Further design and operations experience occurred with participation in missions such as Odin and Radioastron.

Canada's first official partnership in a space astronomy mission began with the NASA FUSE and ESA Lyman working groups, ultimately flown in 1999 as FUSE, with Canadian guide cameras. The experience and reputation from this led us to opportunities such as our role in JWST (as well as other proposals that did not get selected). A Canadian proposal for a UV telescope (CUVIT) for the CSA Scisat program got as far as a Phase-A, but was not selected for flight. However, it led directly to our partnership in Astrosat, and working with ISRO as new partner. Canada later developed and flew its own MOST mission, as well as currently operating BRITe constellation satellites. A few Canadians were significantly involved in team science with ESA missions, e.g., Planck (analysis tools) and Herschel (hardware and software subsystems).

Canadians were, and continue to be, successful users of IUE, HST, Chandra, Newton, Spitzer, and a series of other X-ray missions. Access to space facilities has been, and remains, a vital aspect of Canadian astronomy research. Canadian high tech industry has developed expertise in a useful range of space instrumentation. As a result, Canada is well-known as a space-faring community, and has become a valued (if minor) partner in significant space astronomy missions.

While MOST and BRITe are all-Canadian, they are simple instruments with specialized science capability. The other missions and partnership noted here all serve a very wide range of science, and have been of high interest to many Canadian astronomers. As we look to the future, the balance between missions with broad science capability, and those that offer investigations of high but specialized interest, needs to be judged carefully. Further, as many missions now

perform large surveys, with less or no time for PI proposals, the science returns to Canada also need careful consideration.

Another related capability emerged as CADC became one of three host sites for HST data. CADC worked closely with NASA and ESA, and developed many processes for data enhancement and delivery that have become standard. CADC continues this role for many archives – both ground- and space-based - and is an essential part of any new facility in our LRP. Its funding, mandate, and evolution needs to be part of our future.

The CSA act of 1990 contains the function to *'plan, direct, manage and implement programs and projects relating to scientific or industrial space research and development and the application of space technology.'* During the subsequent decade the agency promoted and funded a number of space science missions with its A-base budget. In astronomy and related fields, we became partners in Odin, FUSE, Planck, Herschel, Astrosat, MOST, and JWST. The process was - and remains - ad-hoc, although subject to advice from the JSSA/JCSA science-based committee for astronomy. With strong urging from this committee, CSA initiated funding for science support to researchers, but here too, there is no mandated provision for such funding, as is the case in NASA, for example.

The current decade

Over the past decade or more, the funding available for space science has dwindled as the overall CSA budget remained more or less constant, but much of it was mandated to support the Astronaut program, ISS membership, Canadarm, and the Radarsats. Funding has been available for concept and technical studies for future astronomy missions, but with little possibility of moving these to hardware and flight. The decade of LRP2010 has seen only one minor new astronomy flight mission contribution: the metrology system for Hitomi.

There are several issues facing the way forward for space astronomy in Canada.

1. CSA has very limited budget to support space astronomy, and none actually earmarked for flight missions. It comes nowhere near the funding implied by the priorities in LRP2010.

2. Any mission not within these funds must be approved by the federal ministry (currently ISED). This requires the right timing, political direction, and negotiation with CSA. Lobbying by stakeholders is needed, but within the political process and priorities of the day. Government decisions in recent years have been made with minimal (if any) consultation with stakeholders, and have often appeared very naive.

3. All space missions need commitment many years in advance. It has been wasteful to undertake studies without a proper process, budget, or down-select schedule. Efforts to allocate space-science funding at an appropriate level (of order \$1B per decade), along with the autonomy of CSA to use them, have been ignored.

4. Most of our space astronomy missions have been partnerships at the ~5% level, led by other agencies. While this has given us access to mission planning and operation, it also leaves us at the mercy of schedules, delays, and issues we cannot control. Canada has the potential and the initiative to lead missions of moderate size once in a decade or so, but these have yet to happen.

5. Canada has an excellent reputation in space astronomy, both scientifically and technically. But in recent years we also have the reputation of failing to fund our opportunities, to the extent that other agencies now do not trust us as partners. This erosion of credibility is a serious threat to our future.

6. Shortage of funds has in several instances led to hardware or partnership issues. A lack of spares and choice of lower-qualified parts led to pre-launch and on-orbit failures of the UVIT detectors. In the case of Hitomi the design was rushed, and required extra calibration to be workable, and we had to get JAXA to pay half the bill anyway. The JWST etalon design was flawed and eventually was replaced with the simpler delivered elements now in NIRISS, but the process was wasteful and embarrassing. These have all led to erosion of our reputation, and must be avoided in future project management.

The early days of CSA allowed us to provide hardware for FUSE, JWST, Astrosat in a timely and reasonably-funded manner. And fly MOST. The process was always ad-hoc, partly driven by reacting to initiatives and schedules led by other agencies. Those days are now past, and the future decade has no committed mission. We need to find a way for LRP2020 to have its intended effect.

In short, the status quo lacks process, funding, and vision. The situation has to change if we are to have a significant future in space in our LRP2020.

Some detailed history.

LRP2010 had a dark energy mission as the top priority, labelled at \$100m (2010) price range.

The following ensued:

1. **Euclid** was already under way. CSA supported a few individuals to participate in Euclid plenary and team meetings. It was clear right away that there was no hardware contribution available, especially at the LRP-suggested level. It was also noticeable that CSA was not regarded as a reliable partner by the Euclid team, as the chronic shortage of funds was apparent to all, even then. There was interest in Canada providing short-wavelength ground survey data, and CFHT and PanSTARRS were approached, both without success for the survey scale wanted. Eventually, via the CFIS survey program, a small group of Canadians has been accepted into the very large Euclid team. This is far from the LRP goal of major DE mission participation.

2. Participation in **WFIRST** was then pursued, bearing in mind the late entry and lessons learned from the Euclid experience. CSA funded studies of a range of mission contributions, in full consultation with NASA, and these were narrowed down for more detailed study, with the expectation that one or two wanted contributions would be offered. CSA engaged a project leader and team of astronomy advisors to participate in the process. The lack of funding for significant hardware persisted, but a proposal for an IFS contribution acceptable to NASA was in CSA's new funding request to the government. At the time, WFIRST NASA costs escalated, and a review placed the IFS on the descope list. There were further negotiations to save the IFS, with and without Canada, but eventually the government did not approve the funding and WFIRST was taken off CSA's wish list, after several years and ~\$2m were spent on the effort. Discussions on minor ways to be in the mission continue, but again the result is nowhere near the level of the LRP goal.

3. The Canadian wide field UV-blue telescope (thence named **CASTOR**) emerged from an extensive CSA concept study as a 1-metre-class wide field high-resolution telescope. The concept has had wide international interest as a significant UV facility to follow HST, GALEX, and UVIT, with science applications far beyond the DE support for Euclid and WFIRST that drove it initially. The cost is more than the LRP nominal amount, and has always been seen as a major difficulty, given the inadequate CSA budget. Further technical studies (detectors and optical coatings) advanced the mission, and the LRP-MTR called for a phase 0 study to clarify the design and cost, as it remained the only way to fulfil the LRP2010 top priority for space. Currently CASTOR has completed an extensive SMS, equivalent to a phase 0, and also has attracted serious and major partnership possibilities with IIA-ISRO and JPL-NASA. There is also significant interest in the UK and Japan. It is now regarded as urgent that CSA negotiate these partnerships and commit to the mission. Here too more than \$2m have been spent on extensive studies and science team work.

A leadership share of this potential partnership is in discussion, and will require of order the nominal major funding that LRP2010 mentioned.

In other categories, the following histories are relevant

SPICA

Over the decade from 2008 to 2018, the CSA invested over \$2.5 M in the SPICA project to establish and preserve a major role for Canada in the SAFARI instrument. As a result of this investment Canada is positioned to build the mission-critical, high resolution spectrometer of the leading infrared space observatory of the coming decades. Furthermore as a founding member of the SAFARI consortium, Canada's return on investment will be at least twice that of the highly successful Herschel space observatory. Canada is seen as a partner of choice and is now positioned to fully exploit the SPICA mission. This therefore remains a project that will soon need Canadian commitment and funding. It is encouraging that a CSA contract has just (July 2019) been awarded to ABB to continue development of FTS hardware.

LiteBIRD

Canada plays a key role in the JAXA CMB polarization mission, LiteBIRD, with hardware, software, and data analysis contributions. The Canadian DfMux bolometer readout system, first demonstrated with CSA funding on the EBEX stratospheric balloon mission, is a key element of the telescope. One risk for the project is that the JAXA cost cap has not allowed for scenarios where a foreign contributor opts out. This means that a failure to move forward in the US, Europe, or Canada with the planned contributions will jeopardize the mission.

With some \$1.5 spent on studies, now, LiteBIRD had not yet been conceived in 2010 and was not considered for LRP2010. CMB polarization appeared as the highest ranked mid-scale space project in MTR2015. It is noted that an RFP appeared for a Phase 0 study for LiteBIRD in July 2019, although it still does not imply a commitment to fund the flight mission.

The way forward and the LRP

The central issue for our participation in space astronomy is the lack of funding and process. Heyl, Gallagher, and Caiazzo led an extensive white paper on this in 2018, with suggested examples of how a responsible program might be run, and noting the inadequate CSA budget in comparison with other agencies. Since then, there has been little change. The CSA budget remains unable to support a viable and worthy program of space science, and is directed in some detail by the federal ministry of the day. Space projects are chosen by political priorities, with no open participation by stakeholders, and uninformed announcements of cost and schedule. CSA are aware of our priorities and opportunities, and support them with uncommitted studies, but have failed to fund them to flight. The task of the astronomy community has been to bring the message to the government, and lobby for individual missions. Given the long lead time for space missions, and the need to appeal to political drivers (and ministries) that change in shorter times, we have no guarantee of success, and the effort is endless.

CSA have recently encouraged us to find other sources of funding, essentially abdicating their role of stewardship of space science, as the only path that may help in the current situation. Given the history and mandate of other funding sources (CFI, NSERC, even NRC or Provincial) and the cost of space missions, this is challenging. It also perpetuates the undesirable process of chasing individual (possibly competing) opportunities rather than having a viable sustained program and process.

With the exception of MOST and BRITE, all our space missions to date have been as minor partners (5% or less) in other agencies' missions. While this gives us seats at the big tables, and the chance to 'hit above our weight' it also places us at the mercies of delays and escalations we cannot influence. There is some strength to joining an international large mission in that CSA feels pressure and an obligation to stay the course. But that too has backfired in that CSA is now reluctant to commit to new international missions, and our reputation as a partner has suffered as a result.

LRP2020 should and will set out priorities and ambitions for a balanced program for the country. But it also needs to have clear and strong recommendations, primarily to the federal government, on the status and needs of the CSA to pursue a viable and worthy space science program, clearly supported by our community. In the absence of any such program and funding, it will be wise to suggest different scenarios and funding sources. It should also involve participation by and discussion with the Space Advisory Board, the chief science advisor to the government, and the science advisors to CSA, NRC, and other government entities. It is highly desirable to formulate a broad space science policy and process, of which astronomy is just a part. Somewhere in the range of 30-40% is an appropriate astronomy share of a science budget of \$100m per year, based on LRP studies from the past decade. A shared science budget will require a process and collaboration among stakeholders that is potentially useful, and will also allow flexible spending

profiles among different projects over time. This approach is already under discussion with the current CSA science advisor, and indeed was the background theme of the 2017 space workshop in Montreal.

This level of funding and commitment does not exist at CSA now. The numbers suggested here will support a careful and selected program, albeit still a factor of several below what NASA, ESA, and other agencies spend, per capita, on space science. It is quite affordable within the Canadian economy, and will inspire and retain the best scientists and engineers, our youth, be a source of public pride and interest, and will keep Canadian high tech industry active and competitive. Such a program will be a legacy of the government that instigates it, long beyond their term of office. Canada will rightfully be a member of the world-wide community of nations doing science in space. Without it, our downward spiral will accelerate, and it will be even harder to recover. LRP2020 will fail in whatever space priorities that emerge from its process.

There are three missions that are ready, and face deadlines for funding and participation now, after the expenditure of years and many \$m by CSA, contractors, and science teams, as described in the detailed notes above. LRP2020 needs to endorse these (CASTOR, LiteBIRD, SPICA) urgently, if we are not to lose out in all the ways noted. The costs for these - hardware, data processing, science support – are roughly \$180m (depending on partnerships in discussion), \$35m, and \$40m, respectively, through the decade. A budget of \$40m/year would cover these, plus the hardware for several new initiatives during the 2020s. That said, a notable issue with LRP2010 was stating costs that turned out to be significantly wrong, and stating deadlines or criteria for continuing that also turned out to be inapplicable.

Serious attention should be paid to alternative ways of pursuing a space science program, to the current CSA paradigm. These might include

1. NRC mandate for astronomy/science from space as well as the ground.
2. Having it a part of the CFI or even NSERC budgets
3. Responsibility for ACURA backing and support.
4. A specific strong endorsement and engagement by the SAB
5. Provincial and industry endorsement/investment
6. Working with OGD such as DND on payloads of common interest
7. Possible pay-per-use scenarios? Crowd-funding?

Some of these may be inadequate or unrealistic, but having such considerations laid out in the LRP may help prod some change, or at least offer suggestions as well as complaints. As always, there is political danger in appearing entitled, or opening the door to that criticism. Space science is for everyone - jobs, public interest, and Canada's place in the world, and astronomy is a major factor in that. Our ambitions and opportunities are very affordable, and should be precious to all.

LRP2020 needs to address the following aspects of our future in space.

1. Funding flight hardware. There are rules and processes for awarding CSA contracts, which may be different if the funds originate elsewhere. Similar considerations may arise in international partnerships. Non-space-agency opportunities for space are likely to ramp up in the next decade.
2. It is important that the astronomy community (teams, or committees such as JCSA) be involved, and to have ongoing formal responsibility through the entire process.
3. Support funding for science analysis has had a long history of uncertainty and negotiation for individual missions. It would be useful to study how other countries do this, and their benefits and successes.
4. Operations, processing, distribution, and archiving of data are an essential part of success and need proper funding, preparation, and teamwork.
5. Outreach and publicity have generally been neglected or done poorly. Scientists and teams should be involved and obliged to spend time and money on this. The payback potential is enormous.
6. Non-orbital investigations (balloon and rocket flights) can play important roles in an LRP. Also, low-cost satellites (microsats, cubesats, with shared launches) are likely to provide attractive opportunities in the coming decade. Nevertheless, larger and more expensive missions need to be core to our ambitions too.
7. Science return can have many forms and LRP should consider the balance among them for missions we join (or don't join):
 - a. Designing instrumentation for Canadian interests/expertise
 - b. Participation in guaranteed instrument science team time
 - c. Share of proposal time
 - d. Participation in survey planning and operations
 - e. Team membership for specialized goals or missions
 - f. Privileged access to survey data
8. Ultimately we need a balanced portfolio of mission involvement that enables the science we see ahead, and benefits a broad community. A space budget needs to cover the points above in a way that is efficient, open, fair, and affordable. A detailed list of missions we can name now, along with implied priorities, is not the right way forward. Nor is a process that relies on the politics of the day.